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Interdisciplinary collaborative learning of creativity and projects

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effect of interdisciplinary collaborative learning on creativity and communication. Students received lectures regarding Internet of things, big data, cloud computing, mechatronics, sensors, embedded systems, and cyber physical systems, as well as training in creative thinking strategies such as brainstorming and six thinking hats. Two classes of students participated in the study. In the experimental class (n=43), undergraduate engineering students (n=22) were partnered with graduate students from digital learning (n=21), whereas the comparison class (n=41) consisted of only undergraduate engineering students

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without interdisciplinary collaboration. In both classes, activities were conducted in groups. Each group created an interdisciplinary project. The data included their responses of using the creative thinking strategies and project proposal. The results found that the experimental class scored significantly higher in both the six thinking hats and brainstorming strategies than the comparison class. Moreover, the groups in the experimental class presented higher quality of proposal and provided considerably more descriptions of their projects. Through the interdisciplinary collaboration, engineering students were able to analyse a problem and examine a piece of work from multiple perspectives, create more ideas, and enhance written communication skills.

Conference Key Areas: engineering education research, curriculum development

Keywords: creativity, interdisciplinary collaboration, smart manufacturing

INTRODUCTION

This study investigated the effect of interdisciplinary collaborative learning on creativity and communication. Previous studies have revealed that engineering students are not comfortable thinking creatively, considering their designs for real-world contexts [1], and communicating effectively [2]. Council on Competitiveness (2005) has identified creativity or innovation as a major keystone of a knowledge economy [3]. We must equip engineering students not only with analytical and technical skills, but also with creative thinking [1]. The effort was mainly through art or design studio. Moreover, one of the factors that significantly affect engineering graduates' success in the workplace is oral and written communication [4]. Ford and Riley (2003) summarized four common approaches to enhance engineering students' communication skills: (1) integrating communication instruction within engineering curricula and including writing assignments within engineering courses, (2) collaborative instruction between engineering departments and communication departments, (3) promoting technical communication minor, and (4) establishing supporting systems such as communication and writing centers [2].

Previous effort on enhancing engineering students' creativity and communication was mainly through art or collaboration with the communication programs [1,2]. Inspired by McNair, Newswander, Boden and Borrego's (2011) interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary teaming approach [5], the current study created a course co-instructed by faculty from the education and engineering departments. The course focused on topics of Industry 4.0 and creative thinking. The graduate students from education and undergraduate students from engineering formed interdisciplinary teams that mimic the cross-functional and cross-disciplinary team structure of industry. They had to collaborate closely in all creativity activities and to write a proposal as they would work in the industry. Their performance in creativity and writing through this interdisciplinary collaboration was evaluated.

1 METHOD

1.1 Participants

Two classes of students participated in the study. In the experimental class (n=43), undergraduate engineering students (n=22) were partnered with graduate students

from digital learning (n=21), whereas the comparison class (n=41) consisted of only undergraduate engineering students without interdisciplinary collaboration. The engineering students were junior or senior students, mostly from mechanical engineering and a few from electrical engineering. In both classes, activities were conducted in groups. The group sizes were controlled between 3 to 4 students. Each group created an interdisciplinary project, wrote up a proposal, and carried out the project.

1.2 Instruction

According to Borrego and Newswander (2008), for a cross-disciplinary engineering education collaboration to be successful, the participating parties should mutually understand and appreciate the nature of knowledge in each other's academic disciplines [6]. To build up this understanding, two faculty members from the education department and two from the engineering department as well as two students from each department have met every week since the semester before the course. All course content and activities were created, tested, and modified together.

The course met three hours a week for 10 weeks. Students received lectures regarding Internet of things, big data, cloud computing, mechatronics, sensors, embedded systems, and cyber physical systems, as well as training in creative thinking strategies such as brainstorming and six thinking hats. The discussing topics in the creativity activities were all based on the lecture topics and contributed to their team projects. At the end of a lecture, each group practiced the creative thinking strategies and attempted to integrate the lecture content into their project through brainstorming or six thinking hats. The group projects were chosen from the following topics: smart production in car industry (AGV, smart machine arm, and object identification system), intelligent vending machine, Gamebike (combining gaming and biking), and intelligent storage/ retrieval systems. The students had to turn in a proposal at the 10th week. They then spent another 8 weeks to carry out the proposal.

The education students played multiple roles as users, project managers and trainers for human resource. They were expected to learn engineers' perspectives from the engineering students and gain experience in leading a project and human resource training and development. The engineering students played a role as engineer. They learned to communicate with engineers from other fields such as electronic engineering, mechanical engineering and education. They would learn users' and managers' perspectives from the education students.

1.3 Data collection and analysis

The performance of the two classes in creativity and proposals was compared. Their responses of using brainstorming strategy were graded based on quantity/ the number of ideas (0-5), appropriateness to the topic (0, 1), practicality (0, 1), and uniqueness (0-3). The scores ranged between 0 and 10. For the six thinking hats strategy, the criteria were quantity/ the number of ideas (0-6), appropriateness to the perspectives of the hats (0-6), and uniqueness (0-3). The scores ranged between 0 and 15. Finally, the proposal was graded by two instructors with inter-rater reliability .83, and their length/word counts were calculated. The scores were compared using the t-tests.

2 RESULT

2.1 Creativity

The data of the experimental class showed that the digital learning students performed significantly better than the engineering students in the use of the six thinking hats strategy, but not in the use of brainstorming (Table 1). The education students were more able to evaluate a case or problem from different perspectives. However, they created about the same amount of ideas as the engineering students. Among the engineering students, the experimental class scored significantly higher in both the six thinking hats and brainstorming strategies than the comparison class (Table 2). In other words, even though both groups received the same creativity training, the experimental group, working with the digital learning students, were able to perform significantly better.

Table 1. Performance of creativity thinking between the engineering and digital learning students

	Engineering (n=21)	Education (n=20)	t(39)	p
Brainstorming	7.78(1.40)	8.24 (1.01)	1.21	.23
6 thinking hats	10.96 (1.27)	14.22 (7.28)	2.02	.05

Table 2. Performance of creativity thinking between the engineering students in two groups

	Experimental group (n=21)	Comparison group (n=48)	t(67)	p
Brainstorming	7.78 (1.40)	6.83(1.50)	2.45	.017
6 thinking hats	10.96 (1.26)	6.63(2.06)	10.09	<.001

2.2 Proposal writing

In comparing the proposal done by both groups, the teams in the experimental group presented higher quality of proposal and provided considerably more descriptions of their projects than those in the comparison group, $t(12.68)=4.13$, $p=.001$.

3 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Through the interdisciplinary collaboration, engineering students were able to analyze a problem and examine a piece of work from multiple perspectives, create more ideas, and enhance written communication skills. The results revealed that student interdisciplinary teaming is a successful approach to prepare engineers for the global and knowledge economy. The student collaboration creates invaluable learning experience. Future curricula may consider to offer such authentic learning experiences.

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